

Sorption of Nitrophenols on Acid-treated Hydrated Zirconium(IV) Oxide

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The parameters like surface area, anion content and OH^- ion exchange capacity of chemically-pretreated (HClO_4 and CH_3COOH) hydrous zirconium(IV) oxide were determined. The sorption of aqueous 2,4-dinitrophenol and picric acid on the substrates of surface-phase pH 3.0–7.5 was found to depend on pH of the substrates, time and temperature. The mechanism of sorption has been shown to be anion - exchange sorption and weak chemical interactions.

Hydrated zirconium(IV) oxide (HZO) has isoelectric point¹ at pH 6.7. The cation and anion exchange behaviour of the oxide have been investigated^{2–4}. It has been shown that pretreatment of the oxide with an acid leads to a surface-phase, which has a pH (internal or effective pH) different from that of the bulk solution⁵. In continuation of the earlier studies⁶ on the chemical pretreatment of HZO, we now report the results on the equilibrium adsorption of 2,4-dinitrophenol and picric acid from aqueous solutions, under various experimental conditions, on hydrated zirconium(IV) oxide of various surface-phase pH.

Results and Discussion

Time-variation data (0.10–2.00 mmol dm^{-3} of the solutes, 10 min–24 h, pH 3.0–7.5) reveal significant adsorption in the early stages with equilibrium almost in 24 h (Fig. 1). Temperature variation studies ($30\text{--}60 \pm 1^\circ$, 6 h, pH 3.0–7.5) show exothermic nature with low isosteric heats of adsorption (Table 1). The pH-variation studies ($30 \pm 1^\circ$, 24 h) showed maximum adsorption of 2,4-DNP at pH 5.0 on HZO(p) and pH 5.5 on HZO(a). Maximum sorption of PA was shown at pH 5.5 on both types of HZO. Here, pH means the initial surface-phase pH of the HZO sample and not the equilibrium value. At pH > 5.5, the adsorption gradually decreased and was almost negligible at pH 7.0–8.0. The adsorption was also negligible at

Fig. 1. Time-variation adsorption of 2,4-dinitrophenol HZO(p) from aqueous solution on HClO_4 -treated hydrated Zr^{IV} oxide; temp. = $30 \pm 1^\circ$, pH = 5.0.

a concentration of $2.00 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$. The ion-inhibiting effect on the adsorption was in the order : $\text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^-$. Desorption studies indicated reversible nature of adsorption. Desorption of DNP was more than that of PA and it increased with increase in pH of HZO.

Several authors^{4,7} pointed out that the addition of an acid to an oxide system involves change of the electrical double layer (primary step) followed by slow secondary reactions. HZO has two strongly acidic centers with $\text{p}K_1$ 7.2 and $\text{p}K_2$ 10.3. The net-

TABLE 1—HEAT OF ADSORPTION (ISOSTERIC) (Q , kJ mol^{-1}) OF 2,4-DINITROPHENOL ON ACID-TREATED HYDRATED ZIRCONIUM(IV) OXIDE

pH of the substrate : HZO(p), 5.0; HZO(a), 5.5; Time of contact = 6 h

x/m (M/g) $\times 10^6$	Q_1 (30–40°)		Q_2 (40–50°)		Q_3 (50–60°)	
	HZO(p)	HZO(a)	HZO(p)	HZO(a)	HZO(p)	HZO(a)
10.0	50.6	64.5	88.7	61.9	122.4	105.6
15.0	72.2	55.5	70.4	48.76	99.7	87.6
20.0	73.6	45.6	49.9	44.2	78.2	102.3
25.0	61.2	33.5	52.3	32.0	80.1	—
30.0	56.1	34.2	38.7	58.4	68.3	—
35.0	43.1	38.3	45.0	—	65.4	—
40.0	50.2	—	38.7	—	58.1	—
45.0	48.9	—	24.3	—	51.2	—
50.0	42.2	—	31.6	—	67.6	—
55.0	38.4	—	37.3	—	—	—

TABLE 2—SYNTHESIS AND COMPOSITION OF HYDRATED ZIRCONIUM(IV) OXIDE OF VARYING SURFACE PHASE pH

Temp. = $30 \pm 3^\circ$, Volume of acid added for pretreatment = 50 ml, Time = 24 h

Surface-phase pH of the oxide	Strength of the acid added for pretreatment (M)		pH of wash-liquid		Anion content of the samples		OH ⁻ ion exchange capacity (mequiv)		Surface area ($S \pm 2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$)	
	HClO ₄	CH ₃ COOH	HClO ₄	CH ₃ COOH	ClO ₄ ⁻	CH ₃ COO ⁻	HClO ₄	CH ₃ COOH	HClO ₄	CH ₃ COOH
	3.0	0.40	2.20	2.8	2.9	0.190	0.210	0.80	0.30	—
3.5	0.25	2.10	3.0	3.0	0.176	0.190	0.70	0.25	—	—
4.0	0.10	2.0	3.7	4.1	0.156	0.150	0.60	0.20	290	215
4.5	0.06	1.0	4.2	5.3	0.090	0.130	0.58	0.18	—	—
5.0	0.04	0.50	4.9	5.8	0.060	0.120	0.53	0.15	270	200
5.5	0.02	0.20	5.1	6.0	0.045	0.100	0.50	0.13	—	—
6.0	0.018	0.10	5.8	6.5	0.029	0.081	0.46	0.12	340	230
7.0	0.015	0.08	6.7	7.1	0.017	0.060	0.40	0.10	355	260
7.5	0.010	0.05	7.3	7.6	0.013	0.040	0.38	0.08	—	—

Surface area and pore size of HZO before acid treatment : $340 \pm 2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, 100–200 mesh.

work of HZO on pretreatment with a acid like HClO₄ and CH₃COOH may react or coordinate with H⁺-ions of the acid, incorporating the diffusable acid-anions (ClO₄⁻ and CH₃COO⁻) and imparting anion-exchange behaviour to the substrate :

It is natural to assume that concentration of the diffusable ions will increase with increase in concentration of the acid for the pretreatment (Table 2).

The pK_a values (at 25°) and the pH-transition interval (in parenthesis) of the nitrophenols are as follows⁸ : 2,4-dinitrophenol, 4.13 (pH 2.0–4.0); 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 0.38 (pH 0.6–1.5).

Mechanism of adsorption : The nitrophenols may be adsorbed on HZO by (i) ion-exchange of their anions with the anions of the chemically-pretreated HZO, and (ii) weak chemical interactions between the surface active points of HZO surface and the adsorbate molecules of the solution. A predominant ion exchange nature is indicated by fast adsorption, low values of the isosteric heats of adsorption (Table 1), decrease in adsorption of the solutes in the presence of electrolytes and certain desorption characteristics.

The nitrophenols in their favourable range of adsorption (pH 3.0–5.5) are essentially in the anionic state, and appear to be the principal adsorbing species in this range. At pH < 5.0, the concentration of the anions (ClO₄⁻/CH₃COO⁻) on the substrate surface

increases and so the ionic species of the solutes decrease, causing a decline in adsorption at pH < 5.0. At pH > 5.5, the proportion of the exchangeable anions on the substrate surface ($\text{ClO}_4^-/\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-$) decreases with increasing pH. Moreover, the protonation and exchange reactions (eqn. 1) take place at higher pH and cause decline in the adsorption.

The adsorption of the solutes in the pH range of 6.5–7.5 may be interpreted in terms of lowering of pH of the system on the addition of aqueous solutions of the nitrophenols (Table 3). Another factor responsible for the adsorption of the solutes on HZO appears to be the surface interactions. At pH < 5.5, it appears that there is hydrogen bonding with the surface sites. The other possible course of adsorption may be the interactions of the π electrons of the aromatic ring with the substrate sites⁹. The NO_2 group does not appear to be directly involved in the interaction as revealed by the greater degree of adsorption of phenol in comparison to nitrobenzene. The nitro group reduces electron density of the ring of the solutes, and so these electron-acceptor adsorbates will be accepted by HZO with negative surface field and active sites¹⁰. Picric acid is a stronger acid ($K_a = 4.2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) than DNP ($K_a = 7.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$). If the relation, coverage factor (C.F.) = 1.2×10^{-7} (ionic weight)^{2,93}

is used¹¹, the C.F. of DNP and PA comes out to be 0.51 and 0.98, respectively. The acid treatment and hence adsorbed anions (ClO_4^- and CH_3COO^-) appear to lower the isoelectric pH, and, thus modify the sorption behaviour of HZO.

The results point to the utility of acid-pretreatment in enhancing anion-exchange characteristics of HZO. The study also reveals the significance of pH and the adsorbed anions (ClO_4^- and CH_3COO^-) in modifying the adsorption-desorption behaviour on HZO.

Experimental

The original sample of hydrated zirconium(IV) oxide (HZO) was prepared³ by adding 6% aqueous ammonia to 0.1 M ZrOCl_2 solution in 0.1 M HCl. HClO_4 - and CH_3COOH -treated samples (to be designated as HZO(p) and HZO(a) respectively) of surface-phase pH 3.0–7.5 were prepared by washing the original HZO sample (25 g, 100–200 mesh, pH 8.4) with acids (50 cm³) of different strengths (0.010–0.40 N HClO_4 and 0.05–2.20 N CH_3COOH), as described earlier⁶. Surface-phase pH was measured as the bulk pH, when HZO was diluted with water to its 1% equivalent and equilibrated for 30 min. HZO with a surface-phase pH < 3.0 could not be prepared by the above method, as higher concentrations of the acids (0.40 N HClO_4 and 2.2 N CH_3COOH) did not change the surface-phase pH. The surface area, OH^- ion exchange capacity and the anion content (ClO_4^- and CH_3COO^-) of the

TABLE 3—RESULTANT SOLUTE-SUBSTRATE pH IN NITROPHENOL-HZO SYSTEMS*

Amount of HZO = 0.25 g, Volume of the nitrophenol = 25 cm³, Time of contact = 30 min

Surface-phase pH of HZO in aqueous medium	pH of HZO in the aqueous solutions of the nitrophenols							
	2,4-Dinitrophenol				Picric Acid			
	HZO(p)		HZO(a)		HZO(p)		HZO(a)	
	2.00	0.20	2.00	0.20	2.00	0.20	2.00	0.20
	mmol dm ⁻³							
3.0	2.20	2.82	2.85	2.90	2.10	2.40	2.80	2.60
4.0	3.35	3.80	3.80	3.85	3.12	3.75	3.70	3.60
5.0	4.20	4.20	4.80	4.90	3.20	4.08	4.50	4.75
6.0	5.10	5.40	5.90	6.20	5.05	5.15	5.65	6.10
7.0	5.90	6.30	6.30	6.70	5.20	6.00	6.10	6.45
7.5	6.10	6.90	6.80	7.15	5.95	6.80	6.50	7.00

*pH of the aqueous solutions of the nitrophenols (without HZO) were 0.20 mmol dm⁻³: pH 3.10 (DNP) and pH 3.00 (PA); 2.00 mmol dm⁻³: pH 4.60 (DNP) and pH 4.00 (PA).

samples were determined^{7,8}. For ready reference, the characteristic parameters of the pre-treated samples are presented in Table 2.

The solutes, 2,4-dinitrophenol and picric acid, after three crystallisation from ethanol-water (1 : 1, v/v) were dried at $80 \pm 1^\circ$ for 12 h. From the stock solution of the nitrophenols in water ($2.00 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$), solutions ($80\text{--}5 \text{ cm}^3$) were withdrawn, diluted to 100 cm^3 and estimated colorimetrically after addition of 0.1 N NaOH at 385 nm in a Carl-Zeiss Spekol spectrophotometer. The absorbance was not affected by change in pH, acid used for pretreatment or elevated temperatures ($30\text{--}60^\circ$), during the estimation.

Adsorption experiments were carried out by equilibrating HZO (0.10 g) with the nitrophenol solutions of known concentration, thermostated at desired temperature for a specific period of time and shaking intermittently. The concentration of the final solution was determined after centrifugation. The amount adsorbed at equilibrium was calculated by difference.

Adsorption studies in presence of electrolytes (NaNO_3 , Na_2SO_4 and Na_3PO_4) were conducted with the same concentrations, of the adsorbate and the electrolytes, i.e. 1.00 , 0.60 and $0.20 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$. These conditions allow the anions (NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-}) to compete for the adsorption sites on the HZO. The procedure adopted was the same as reported earlier⁹. Desorption studies of the nitrophenols (1.00 , 0.60 and $0.10 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$) adsorbed on HZO ($\text{pH } 3.0\text{--}7.5$, $30 \pm 1^\circ$, 24 h) were carried out with the inorganic electrolytes ($0.001\text{--}0.1 \text{ M}$), as described earlier⁹.

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